

Figured Magic Squares of Order 26 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure

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Abstract

Recently, author constructed even order magic squares from orders 6 to 20 with different styles and models, for examples the order 20 is with 1616 magic squares, order 18 with 810 magic squares, etc. These can be seen at [31, 32, 33, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37]. The aim is to proceed for the further orders of magic squares. In this work there are few examples of magic squares given as figures of order 26. A systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares and bordered magic rectangles (BMR) of orders 4, 6, 8 etc forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. The presentations is in figures instead of numbers. The readers can find replies in numbers from references given above. For the orders multiples of 4, we can always write magic squares with equal sums blocks of magic squares of order 4. This procedure is very helpful for the orders of type $2p$, where p is a prime number, for examples, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, etc. For the orders like 18, 30, etc. we can make good external blocks with order 4, and for orders like 16, 20, 28, 32, etc. we can make good external borders of order 6, and so on.

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Magic Squares of Order 26	4
2.1	Bordered Square of Order 26	4
2.2	Magic Squares of Order 26 With BMR	6
2.3	Cornered Magic Squares of Order 4	9
2.4	Closed Border of Order 4	20
2.5	Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6	32
2.6	Closed Border of Order 6	39
2.7	Cornered Magic Squares of Order 8	44
2.8	Closed Border of Order 8	51
2.9	Cornered Magic Squares of Order 10	58
2.10	Closed Border of Order10	67
2.11	Magic Squares of Orders 12 and 14	70
2.12	Extra Examples	75
3	Appendix	81
4	Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers	82

1 Introduction

The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

Recently, the author [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37] constructed magic squares of even orders from 8 to 20 using **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on two aspects:

- (i) Using **magic rectangles** or **bordered magic rectangles**.
- (ii) Using algebraic formula like $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^2, \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$.

For the above magic squares no construction procedure is explained. The aim is to proceed further orders of magic squares. In this work, a systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares and bordered magic rectangles (BMR) of orders 4, 6, 8 etc forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. For the orders multiples of 4, we can always write magic squares with equal sums blocks of magic squares of order 4. This procedure is very helpful for the orders of type $2\mathbf{p}$, where \mathbf{p} is a prime number, for examples, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, etc. For the orders like 18, 30, etc., we can make good external blocks with order 4, and for orders like 16, 20, 28, 32, etc. we can make good external borders of order 6, and so on. There is no explanations for the orders 6, 8, 10 and 12. The real construction starts from the order 14.

The whole the work is done manually, without use of any programming language, except for the constructions of small blocks of **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on the software due to H. While. Later, these BRM's are readopted according to distribution of each magic square. The distribution of magic squares or bordered magic rectangles is based on **half-sequential** numbers. By **half-sequential** numbers we understand that the total numbers in each case are divided in two equal parts. First part is one sequence and second part is another sequence. Due to **half-sequential** numbers, it is not possible to construct all orders **bordered**

magic rectangles. In Appendix 3, there are tables showing the existence of these **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential**. For simplicity, we shall write **BMR** as **bordered magic rectangle**.

2 Magic Squares of Order 26

This section brings in figures (without numbers) magic squares of order 26. In some cases, the constructions are explained.

2.1 Bordered Square of Order 26

Below is a magic square of order 26 already known in the literature. For more details refer author's work [22, 24].

2.2 Magic Squares of Order 26 With BMR

Below are two examples of magic squares of order 26 made with BMR. These are constructed separately. For more details with numbers refer [37].

2.3 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 4

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 4 at the corners. Let's make an external border by putting BMR of order 4×18 in each row and column. In the middle we are left with block of order 17. Writing middle block of order 18 with different types of magic squares, we get magic squares of order 26. See below few examples:

2.4 Closed Border of Order 4

Let's consider 4 equal sums BMR of order 4×18 . Then put them in a symmetric way in external part of the magic squares. We are left with internal block of order 18. Writing middle block of order 18 with different types of magic squares, we get magic squares of order 26. See below few examples:

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2.5 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6

Let's consider an external border, where there are 8 magic squares of order 6 and 8 BMRs of order 4×6 . This gives us an external border with cornered magic squares of order 6. In the middle we are left with block of order 14. Writing middle block of order 14 with different types of magic squares, we get magic squares of order 26. See below few examples:

The last two magic squares are made with little different way, where we have taken directly two BMRs of order 4×26 . The magic squares of order 6 are considered in two different ways.

2.6 Closed Border of Order 6

Let's write a closed external border formed by four equal sums BMR's of order 6×20 . In the middle we are left with block of order 14. Writing this middle blocks of order 14 with different types of magic squares, we get magic squares of order 26. See below few examples:

2.7 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 8 at the corners. Let's make an external border by putting BMR of order 6×12 in each row and column. In the middle we are left with blocks of order 10. Writing middle block of order 10 with different types of magic squares, we get magic squares of order 26. See below few examples:

2.8 Closed Border of Order 8

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 BMR's of order 8×14 . Putting them in rows and columns, we get a closed border of order 8. In the middle we are left with blocks of order 6. Writing middle block of order 6 and different types of magic squares of order 8, we get magic squares of order 22. See below few examples:

2.9 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 10 at the corners. Let's make an external border by putting BMR of order 4×6 with magic square of order 6 in each row and column. In the middle we are left with blocks of order 6. Writing middle block of order 6 in two different ways and external magic squares of order 10 also in different ways, we get magic squares of order 26. See below few examples:

2.10 Closed Border of Order10

Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 BMR's of order 8×18 . Putting them in rows and columns, we get a closed border of order 8. In the middle we are left with blocks of order 6. Writing middle block of order 6 in two different ways, we get magic squares of order 26. See below few examples:

2.11 Magic Squares of Orders 12 and 14

Let's consider two BMRs of order 12×14 , and magic squares of orders 10 and 12. This gives following magic squares of order 26 with different choices of magic squares of orders 12 and 14. See below few examples:

2.12 Extra Examples

Below are few extra examples done individually.

3 Appendix

Below are tables giving the existence of **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential** numbers.

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
6	4×6
8	6×8
10	$4 \times 10, 8 \times 10$
12	$6 \times 12, 10 \times 12$
14	$4 \times 14, 8 \times 14, 12 \times 14$
16	$6 \times 16, 10 \times 16, 14 \times 16$
18	$4 \times 18, 8 \times 18, 12 \times 18$
20	$6 \times 20, 10 \times 20, 14 \times 20, 18 \times 20$
22	$4 \times 22, 8 \times 22, 12 \times 22,$ $16 \times 22, 20 \times 22$
24	$6 \times 24, 10 \times 24, 14 \times 24,$ $18 \times 24, 22 \times 24$
26	$4 \times 26, 8 \times 26, 12 \times 26,$ $16 \times 26, 20 \times 26, 24 \times 26$
28	$6 \times 28, 10 \times 28, 14 \times 28,$ $18 \times 28, 22 \times 28, 26 \times 28$
30	$4 \times 30, 8 \times 30, 12 \times 30, 16 \times 30,$ $20 \times 30, 24 \times 30, 28 \times 30$
32	$6 \times 32, 10 \times 32, 14 \times 32, 18 \times 32,$ $22 \times 32, 26 \times 32, 30 \times 32$
34	$4 \times 34, 8 \times 34, 12 \times 34, 16 \times 34,$ $20 \times 34, 24 \times 34, 28 \times 34, 32 \times 34$

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
36	$6 \times 36, 10 \times 36, 14 \times 36, 18 \times 36,$ $22 \times 36, 26 \times 36, 30 \times 36, 34 \times 36$
38	$4 \times 38, 8 \times 38, 12 \times 38, 16 \times 38, 20 \times 38,$ $24 \times 38, 28 \times 38, 32 \times 38, 36 \times 38$
40	$6 \times 40, 10 \times 40, 14 \times 40, 18 \times 40, 22 \times 40,$ $26 \times 40, 30 \times 40, 34 \times 40, 38 \times 40$
42	$4 \times 42, 8 \times 42, 12 \times 42, 16 \times 42, 20 \times 42,$ $24 \times 42, 28 \times 42, 32 \times 42, 36 \times 42, 40 \times 42$
44	$6 \times 44, 10 \times 44, 14 \times 44, 18 \times 44, 22 \times 44, 26 \times 44,$ $30 \times 44, 34 \times 44, 38 \times 44, 42 \times 44$
46	$4 \times 46, 8 \times 46, 12 \times 46, 16 \times 46, 20 \times 46, 24 \times 46,$ $28 \times 46, 32 \times 46, 36 \times 46, 40 \times 46, 44 \times 46$
48	$6 \times 48, 10 \times 48, 14 \times 48, 18 \times 48, 22 \times 48, 26 \times 48,$ $30 \times 48, 34 \times 48, 38 \times 48, 42 \times 48, 46 \times 48$
50	$4 \times 50, 8 \times 50, 12 \times 50, 16 \times 50, 20 \times 50, 24 \times 50,$ $28 \times 50, 32 \times 50, 36 \times 50, 40 \times 50, 44 \times 50, 48 \times 50$

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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